

DESIGN & EMOTION AS A STRATEGY OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: SESC SÃO PAULO IN THE SOCIAL IMAGINARIES

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ABSTRACT

The paper presented at this Design and Emotion London Conference 2012 concerns the experiments in design, mainly in regard to graphic design as a strategy of social communication, which have been applied in an outstanding institution dedicated to improving the quality of life of people in Brazil: SESC São Paulo. The paper discusses how management of the entity's graphic communication has made use of design & emotion, based on a social dialogic process supported by a scientific methodology of Urban Imaginaries, which has served as a basis for the organization's creative exercise. In this regard the paper emphasizes the importance of the emotive, sensorial, nonmaterial perceptions – on scales that are totally subjective, emotive and therefore out of control – while the methodology used allows for the scientific mapping of these citizen perceptions.

Keywords: Urban Imaginaries, Social Responsibility, citizen, SESC São Paulo.

INTRODUCTION

The work that I am presenting is related to postdoctoral research that I am developing in a joint effort between two Latin American universities: the Universidad Externado de Colômbia, in Bogotá, Colombia, and the Universidade de São Paulo, in Brazil. The study is based on the investigation of Armando Silva, a Colombian researcher who has been studying the Ibero-American urban cultures for more than 20 years, the author of the concept of the urban imaginaries.

By way of Armando Silva's research, applied in various Ibero-American cities, we can understand how

people see their cities and other Ibero-American cities.

The imagined city is often different from the real one, but at the same time it becomes real in the urban imaginaries. For example, the methodology applied by Professor Armando Silva seeks to identify the citizen's sensations and perceptions in regard to subjective qualities such as the color of his/her city, its gender, or the icon that best represents it. In the methodology of the research, these questions are posed to interviewees in questionnaires. The answers have shown that the city of São Paulo is understood as being gray and of the male gender, ceaselessly growing, offering opportunity to all. But when we take an objective look at the city we see a large metropolis which is undebatably a growing city that is transforming day by day, and yet is teeming with colors. The relation established within the urban imaginary, between the color gray and the city, is related to pollution and the myriad concrete buildings.

Figure 1. Edifício Copan, São Paulo imagined

Figure 2. Viaduto do Chá, São Paulo Imagined

Another example, Buenos Aires, is understood by its citizens as a city of the female gender, charming, glamorous, related to tango dancing and seduction, but at the same time a motherly city, that fights for its children. The Plaza de Mayo is a very meaningful site for the citizens of Buenos Aires, and the mothers who protested in this public square and made the world see the atrocities committed in Argentina during the military dictatorship reinforce the imagery of the combative woman.

Figure 3. Plaza de Mayo, Buenos Aires Imagined

The methodology developed to learn about the ways of being urban, as well as the conception of comparative modes of different Ibero-American cities aims to capture the subjective city (which is present in the minds of the people) and the citizens' ways of life, how they comprehend and evidence collective memories of urban themes, such as local happenings, characters, myths, scales of colors and smells, which identify and establish the city's, fabulations, histories and urban legends.

This methodology does not aim to reveal the physical city, but rather the mental one, which exists in the perceptions of the citizens. A subjective city that is realized through interactive psychological mechanisms among citizen collectives. Based on this point of view, the city becomes an imaginary effect of its citizens. As a consequence, this sort of investigation is focused on urban feelings, fears, loves, hates, memories – all the feelings that characterize the city symbolically. Thus, rather than being focused on the architecture and material marks of the physical, concrete city, the primary interest is to establish the profound links between the collective perceptions, the uses of the cities, and the possible strategies for new urban perceptions.

The techniques employed include the construction of a database on the citizens' perceptions, produced by way of quantitative and qualitative research, the comparison of these data with official documents and statistics on the same themes, the collection of images concerning the cities and the citizens, or the point of view of the citizens on the cities based on information circulating in various mass media, works of artistic creation and expression regarding the cities, and, what Professor Armando Silva calls the parallel representations: the audiovisual production on the same research. All of these techniques can be used as basis for interventions on the city.

SESC SÃO PAULO

I will use the large institution where I work as director of the graphic arts department, SESC São Paulo, as a means of exemplifying the concept and applications of the urban imaginaries. The name SESC is an abbreviation for the Portuguese phrase meaning "Social Services for Commerce Workers." It is a nonprofit organization aimed at improving the quality of people's lives through the informal, ongoing education of the public, by means of the promotion of citizenship, art and cultural events, courses, workshops, sports and recreation. By way of 34 cultural and sports centers, 14 of which are located in the city of São Paulo itself, SESC São Paulo offers the possibility of theater shows, concerts, cinema, literature events, exhibitions, activities in the natural environment, social tourism, activities for senior

citizens, recreation, and noncompetitive sports, aimed at social inclusion. In so doing, it engages in physical/sport development, raising awareness in regard to the environment and health, thematic meetings, the promotion of cultural diversity, the

Figure 4. SESC Pinheiros, one of the Units of the SESC

Figure 5. Cultural aticvidades SESC in Sao Paulo

preservation and recovery of memories, communication for education and communitarian actions, while making use of various media, including the SESCSP portal, a publishing house and the SESTV television channel.

The institution's policies are concerned with the valorization of the human individual that takes place during the meetings and events, in the access to high-quality programming. The activities of this institution, founded in the 1940s, have garnered attention on the international scene. At this current moment in which the world is facing a series of global economic crises, the model deployed by SESC has been seen as an example to be studied, as a model that can be implanted elsewhere. Recently *The New York Times* ([http://www.nytimes.com/2012/03/27/arts/brazils-leading-arts-financing-group-shares-the-](http://www.nytimes.com/2012/03/27/arts/brazils-leading-arts-financing-group-shares-the-wealth.html?_r=1&pagewanted=all)

[wealth.html?_r=1&pagewanted=all](http://www.nytimes.com/2012/03/27/arts/brazils-leading-arts-financing-group-shares-the-wealth.html?_r=1&pagewanted=all)) newspaper published a long, front-page article presenting SESC São Paulo as a model of a cultural institution that has been growing in its actions and investments, even while most cultural organizations in the world are shrinking, during this moment of crises.

The main fulcrum of its programs is informal, open, ongoing education aimed at developing the individual as a human being, to become more autonomous and culturally aware, allowing for social inclusion. This informal education is not rigidly organized into courses with tests and grades like a school, rather, the users may select from an open-ended spectrum of choices according to their interests. For this reason it can be characterized as "out of control" since there is no obligatory curriculum and the aim is to provoke the individual to awaken in entirely unexpected ways, which vary from user to user. As the users enjoy the activities, they yield to the constructive energies that arise in these settings, strengthening their role as citizens and members of their communities and families. It is called "ongoing" because it truly is endless, as the activities link together in time, based on past experience, bringing the best successes forward into the future, and allowing them to spread, as people bring their friends, families and acquaintances into the program.

As democratic spaces of social inclusion, the SESC units are open to the entire population, and for this reason the same activity is often shared by workers and business owners, in the same space. The preferential public has always been the workers in the commerce in service sectors, but these centers of culture and leisure are accessible to everyone.

SESC's actions are designed based on the needs of the people, valorizing them; the actions are directed toward continuous education and the development of children and youths, artistic expressions, sporting activities and physical development, leisure, nature and the environment, health, dentistry, digital inclusion and social tourism. In this way, the institution becomes an integral part of each city, each with its unique nuances in regard to its industrialization, longstanding migrational flows, the strengthening of a collective identity, and a wide range of other aspects.

Figure 6. Some of the sports and cultural centers of the SESC

The entity is emblematic of the city of São Paulo, with its cultural and sports centers occupying various districts of the city, having become local references within a polycentric city. From the standpoint of polycentrism, the city is understood, perceived and imagined by the population as being multiple. The concept of the city nowadays no longer involves a single center that is representative of a metropolis, but rather various centers with their own specificities. The notion of polycentrism is related to the public uses of the cities as they are imagined; the city spreads and is decentralized by its own nature. Large thoroughfares cut through the city from north to south, from east to west, and these spaces are no longer experienced in their own right, being used only as paths for reaching one place or another. It is impossible for the citizen to know all of this multimodal reality, rather, he or she lives in one place, commutes to work in another, goes to yet another for shopping or recreation, and the spaces between these nodes hardly exist at all in that person's urban imaginary.

In the city of São Paulo, SESC's cultural and sports centers located in these nodes are true citadels within the urban landscape, polycentric hubs in constant and continuous dialogue with the city, and as the city grows, the institution takes on new contours and grows along with it. These units radically transform the city as well as its imaginaries, and when they are delivered to the public they begin to receive new stimuli in dialogic processes in which the social interpretations subjectively begin to act and to foster new relations with the offer of actions aimed at the construction of citizenship through informal and

continuous education. In this way, the social imaginaries come into play and generate the (out-of-control) effect which is the theme of this conference.

I should mention that each of our units is named after the district it is located in. This is strategic option that reinforces the identity of SESC as an institution integrated with the surrounding community. This strategy dates back about 20 years; before this many of the units were named after the institution's important benefactors and directors, such as "Antonio Carlos Machado Neto." The feeling that this conveyed was very formal and uninviting. Therefore, the strategic decision was to change the names to coincide with the surrounding districts. This conveyed a sensation of belonging, and the good image of the SESC units was more readily spread like an aura into the entire district that surrounded them. We thus see that this decision has much to do with Armando Silva's thinking concerning polycentrism and the concept of urban imaginaries, as the name of the unit itself becomes part the individual's mental construct of a given urban area.

Figure 7. Leisure Activities in SESC

SESC São Paulo has therefore become a symbol of reference in the various districts, serving as a synthesis of each region in completely democratic spaces that are shared by the population. This fact is verified based on the methodology of the applied research, based on questionnaires to map the ways that people practice their citizenship, and the subjective ways in which the citizens see their cities, as developed by Armando Silva. What we are developing at this moment is a deepening of the understanding of how this institution, SESC São

Paulo, has successfully established itself as a highly positive element in urban imaginary. This success is demonstrated by way of the results of quantitative and qualitative research, still underway.

As the manager of the institution's graphic arts department, and at the same time a scientific investigator in the field of social communication, specialized in urban imaginaries, I have had the opportunity to apply the knowledge arising from scientific researches in the daily practice of the communication with the institution's users, and I am currently developing a postdoctoral thesis in which I am studying how SESC is seen in the imaginary of the citizens, based on the theoretical basis developed by Prof. Armando Silva, of the University of Colombia. My aim in the present paper is twofold: first, to demonstrate how we have taken advantage of the scientific studies of urban imaginaries, applying these studies in an institution that provides service to 300 thousand people per week as we conduct our work in the processes of graphic communication, considering relations for the production of immaterial meanings, which are based on urban perceptions strongly linked to the most emotive questions of society; and second, how we are able – supported by an understanding of the social emotions – to construct strategies of social communication directly linked to the effectiveness of the entity's programs, all of which are geared toward social responsibility, even when working with perceptions that are emotional, sensorial, nonobjective, and thus out of control. The study I am currently developing resorts to semiotics and psychoanalysis in order to control these out-of-control aspects.

THE CASE OF SESC BELENZINHO

To exemplify this approach I will take as an example the recently inaugurated unit of SESC Belenzinho: located in São Paulo city's East Zone, its 55-thousand-square-meter facilities were created when a deactivated factory warehouse was transformed into one of the city's most vibrant spaces for culture and sports. The delivery of these facilities to the city modifies the urban meanings, entailing changes in the imaginaries. In recent years the district of Belenzinho – which was formerly an area of the city

rich in meaning, due in great part to the productive power of its industries – had been emptied of its industries, which were transferred to other areas in processes of modernization, and the district became a reservoir of huge abandoned warehouses. Once they

Figure 8. Neighborhood of Belenzinho in São Paulo, before the inauguration of the SESC Belenzinho - Social Imaginary: death and abandonment.

were gone, the Quarta Parada Cemetery became one of the district's most highly significant features. Thus, the urban imaginaries related to Belenzinho were related to abandonment and death. The younger populations moved out of the district, as they did not identify with the place.

Figure 9. Neighborhood of Belenzinho in São Paulo, after the inauguration of the SESC Belenzinho - Social Imaginary: Life - the beach of St. Paulo

SESC Belenzinho was opened in the city's East Zone on December 4, 2010, as a sports and culture complex with six pools, sports courts, gymnasiums and three theater auditoriums, plus a food-service area with the capacity to serve 2500 meals. With its large, organically shaped pools mimicking the curving shoreline of the sea and receiving up to 4000 people

per day during the summer, SESC Belenzinho's facilities began to be subjectively perceived by the population – in an out-of-control perceptual shift – as a sort of urban beach, bringing about a radical shift in the area's urban imaginary. The social imaginaries were immediately transformed from death and abandonment to life and belonging.

The architectural design was conceived in such a way as to emphasize an enormous square right at the entrance to the unit, which makes an interface between the street and the multiple facilities – the square retains the subjective value of a place of great symbolic exchanges. Just as the architectural design of the SESC units is designed for shared life experience, for the carrying out of its programs and for the qualification of the human being, the same line of design in its programming and its communication favors the autonomy of the person, fostering attitudes of questioning, experimentation with conventions, and innovation.

GRAPHIC DESIGN

This brings us to the subject analyzed in the investigation that I am developing in my postdoctoral work, where I take the original methodology of urban imaginaries as a basis for practical developments in social communication working in the field of graphic design, with the aim of supporting the entity's continuing programs for informal education and investment in the constant upgrading of the quality of life of the public segments it serves.

One of the most striking aspects of contemporary society is the large volume of visual information that bombards the individuals daily. With a very wide range of goals, including to inform, to sell, to convince, to charm, to warn, and to incite, this visual avalanche pervades our everyday lives. In this context of excess and immediatism, SESC's communication actions become increasingly relevant and fundamental, with a goal strategically aligned to the organizational mission; namely, to promote continuous education as a prerequisite for personal development and social transformation. In this way, the eminently educational character of SESC's actions pervade all the entity's communication processes, providing creative,

significant and lasting visual experiences for its various segments of users.

Upon understanding the public's mindset in terms of their relations of citizenship and how they see their surroundings, the creative work for the strategy of communication and public relations is structured in the most effective way in order to involve a wide range of sensations, emotions and feelings; to this end, the morphology of the graphic pieces, the colors, and the typography plays an important role.

Figure 10. Visual identity created by graphic designer Chico Homem de Melo for the SESC Arts Circuit.

This logo created by designer Chico Homem de Melo for the SESC Art Circuit accentuates the structure of the stage that traveled to 88 cities, bringing spectacles of theater, music and other performances as part of the Art Circuit. When this traveling show enters a small city or town it takes it over by cultural storm, delivering a high-energy shot of creativity and performance art. The logo's design suggests a portico, a passage, or the demarcation of a space. The logo gained visibility in the various applications and chromatic patterns, with clearly constructivist layouts, which were unfolded in a wide range of supports, such as booths, buses, trucks, T-shirts, brochures, banners, posters and digital media. The materials for publicity and mediation reflected the concepts set forth by the traveling project, including that of inserting artistic appreciation and human development in day-to-day activities and the holding of encounters in the public squares of those cities that do not possess SESC operational units.

The new visual identity of SESC's Dance Biennial was created based on a reflection on the movements of the human body, emphasizing articulations, overlaps and the relation in the proportions among the members. The typographical construction of the logotype was based on this study, with the letters suggesting the movements of dancing bodies and conveying the performative energy featured at the dance biennial. Aimed at stimulating different

Figure 11. Construction and example of the application of the SESC Dance Biennial logo.

interpretations by the observer, while informing and welcoming the public, applications and variations of the logo were developed on supports such as invitations, program guides and a catalog.

The return of the Théâtre du Soleil performance company to Brazil in 2011 for the *The Castaways of Crazy Hope* tour was accompanied by a series of printed matter, such as programs, postcards and a catalog. The large tent set up at SESC's Belenzinho unit was given the visual identity of a spectacle, contextualizing and inserting the public within the scenographic setting.

In each of these cases, even at the moment the public first becomes aware of the program or event, upon

seeing the logo or traveling venue for the first time, they become immediately aware its essential nature. These graphic devices therefore influence how that person will interpret the information about the program or event, and react upon attending it. This is graphic art at the service of communication, by way of how it influences the public's imagination.

RESEARCH

When I linked my goals for academic studies in social communication with the objectives under my responsibility, in the management of SESC São Paulo's graphic arts, there arose a formal experiment in design and emotion, in regard to the ways that concepts of social subjectivity are related through sensations such as love, fear, desire, smell and hope to the goals for communicating the institution's programs vis à vis its users; we thus managed to improve the communicational strategies insofar as they are linked to real feelings in the construction of messages related to SESC's objectives in regard to the public segments it serves.

In this context, I have deepened my studies and am currently working on a postdoctoral proposal under the theme "SESC Imagined – Citizen Perceptions," with the application of methodological research of urban imaginaries at SESC São Paulo as a reference point in the city's imaginary; in this study my aim has been to shed light on how the creative and aesthetic experience fosters new relations of citizenship, and on how such social modifications are reechoed by the citizens themselves, who by way of knowledge and the deepening of their imagetic repertoire gain autonomy to become active agents who generate other citizenship actions.

My own research is an outgrowth of Professor Armando Silva's program of scientific research into urban imaginaries, a wide-ranging international program of a comparative nature which seeks to understand problematics of Latin American and Iberian urban cultures through a transdisciplinary outlook, based on the epistemological tools of anthropology, psychoanalysis, social communication, aesthetics and history. The methodological framework conceived by Prof. Dr. Armando Silva has been

unfolded in multiple productions realized throughout a period of more than two decades in partnerships and agreements with universities and institutions of various cities involved in the scope of the study, with the support of UNESCO and institutions such as the Fundació Antoni Tàpies of Barcelona, SESC São Paulo, and others.

The network of researchers involved in this international investigation springs from centers of investigation concerning the themes of the cities, the urban imaginary and symbolic production, spread throughout Latin America and Spain, beginning with the Universidade Externado de Colombia, with the addition of institutions such as the Universidade de São Paulo (USP); the Universidad de Buenos Aires (UBA), the Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias (FASCO), Ecuador; the Universidad Arcis de Santiago de Chile; the Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana de Iztapalapa de México; the Universidad Católica Boliviana; the Universidad de Lima; the Universidad Mayor de San Andrés de La Paz; the Universidad de la República de Uruguay; UNESCO; the Universidad Internacional de Andalucía, and others.

Prof. Armando Silva's studies began in Bogotá 25 years ago, when graffiti – which shook Paris in 1968 and New York during the 1970s – began to agitate at the Universidade Nacional de la Colombia, with a novel visual style and new urban sense that reverberated on this continent and later in other European countries. This graffiti called attention to the local traditions, instigated the anti-imperialist order and re-created it with new alternatives, in which the form of the message became important, placing rock music on the wall and giving rise to the graffiti-rock movement. In the context of this commotion and repercussion, Prof. Armando Silva was the first theorist to approach graffiti psychoanalytically in terms of its relation with the urban imaginaries.

Upon examining the imaginaries in light of graffiti, a coincidence was found insofar as both cases are public exhibitions of the citizens, the difference being that graffiti is realized in a material form, while the imaginaries are invisible worldviews that act as aesthetic forms of society, and, of course, the imaginaries are not prohibited.

This being the case, the urban imaginaries are made by the citizens, while the artists make public art. But the two phenomena converge. The artists re-create social imaginaries, the citizens project their desires with aesthetic forms.

THEORY

The view of imaginaries as a social construction of reality arises from cognitive mechanisms by the psychic transversality of human nature, from representative logic. The deep structural relations of the mechanisms that underlie linguistics give rise to the three practically universal personal pronouns: I, you and he/she. This microstructure is the basis of a representative logic developed by Charles Sanders Peirce in his triad of firstness, secondness and thirdness, which corresponds to the fundamental triad of Freudian psychoanalysis: the conscious, the preconscious and the unconscious, and the elaboration of a second structural topos: the id, the ego and the superego; these threesomes find echoes in three psychic orders: the Real, the Imaginary and the Symbolic.

Peirce's logical triad can be understood as the deep structural basis for the Urban Imaginaries methodology; the triadic division of the urban imaginaries, by analogy to the phenomenological model becomes: *city, citizen, and the others*. First, the city as a quality where the inhabitants find their possibility of being. Peirce exemplifies firstness as a flash – it is like the world was for Adam, when he opened his eyes for the first time, before making distinctions and becoming aware of his existence.

For its part, secondness is situated in the past. There needs to have been an experience for the advent of a consciousness. Thus, Peirce once again resorts to a biblical example: God said, "Let there be light," and there was light. This duality of firstness added to secondness is existence.

In terms of the urban imaginaries, secondness is potentialized in the citizen.

Thirdness is a third term related to the other two. While in secondness the relation is one of dependence, in thirdness it is one of composition. The third element is always a link, a term, a bridge, a mediation. The sign is the best example of the third element in Peirce's architecture – the sign as a representation. It bears the idea produced and modifies it through otherness. It is a vehicle that comes into the mind from the outside.

The ego, the superego, and the id.
 The imagined city, the real city, the potential city.
 The three persons in grammar: I you, he and she.
 The Hegelian thesis, antithesis and synthesis.
 The Holy Trinity of the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit.

In Armando Silva: The real city, the city imagined from experience, and the city imagined without experience.

By way of the Colombian professor's methodology, the collection of subjective data in field research and how these urban meanings pervade the citizens allows for an understanding of how the citizens perceive their urban centers, of how the cities are represented in their imaginations.

My postdoctoral research adds a new dimension to this approach by displacing the city as a central object of investigation, placing emphasis on the institution – SESC São Paulo – and the public segments it serves, as well as on the modes of representation that are symbolically constructed.

THE CITIZEN WITHOUT THE CITY AND THE CITY WITHOUT THE CITIZEN

One of the aspects examined during the study of the urban imaginaries has to do with two curious phenomena, namely, the occurrence of urbanism without the city, and the existence of the city without urbanism. I will begin by considering the first phenomenon. Urban citizenship can arise outside the city, since even in small towns, distant from any large city there occurs the imagined presence of urban citizenship. Even though they live in the setting of a small town or the countryside, people can develop an urban imaginary that effectively makes them

extensions of a large metropolis. This phenomenon is robustly evidenced by the artistic results of Biennial of Brazilian Naïve Art, a large exhibition held by SESC São Paulo every two years and featuring works of popular art, collected in the most far-flung localities in Brazil, such as small communities, towns, and agricultural areas often distant from any physical urban center. These local artists are known as naïve or primitive artists, as they lack artistic training and yet possess a great desire to register the world, their dreams and their emotions. The work of these artists presents themes that are highly significant in terms of urban imaginaries.

Figure 12. artist Waldomiro de Deus, work *Mundo Bom* [Good World], 1972.

Artists such as Waldomiro de Deus, originally from the interior of Bahia state, inspired by the urban imaginaries, came to São Paulo when he was still a boy, at the age of 12. His work, with strong and vibrant colors reflects the urban thought in its depiction of anthropological and architectural aspects. The mythic, spiritual relation is always present as a key between the urban and the popular. Waldomiro de

Deus is regularized as a key figure in Brazilian naïve art.

Another striking example, in terms of the aesthetic trend I am demonstrating here is the work of popular artist Nilson Machado, from Rondonópolis, in the state of Mato Grosso do Sul. His work entitled *Sem Ninhos* [Without Nests], presented at the 2006 edition of SESC's Biennial of Brazilian Naïve Art, discusses the

Figure 13. artist Nilson Machado, work *Sem Ninhos* [No Nests], 2006.

advance of the cities toward the interior of the forests. Through expressive brushwork and a highly colorful composition, Nilson creates a city as it might look if it were taken over by forest animals, which have lost their place, their space, their reference, their nests.

Figure 14. Artist Tadeu de Lira, work *Corrida de São Silvestre* [The São Silvestre Marathon], 2004.

Artist Tadeu de Lira, from the interior of Paraíba state, in the Brazilian Northeast, has become a leading

figure of Paraíba naïve art. The urban themes are highly present in the artist's imagination, including the city of São Paulo, even though the artist lives in a place completely removed from the large city. At the 2004 edition of the Biennial of Brazilian Naïve Art the artist presented the work *Corrida de São Silvestre* [The São Silvestre Marathon], which depicts the architecture of Paulista Avenue, an icon in the social imaginaries of the city of São Paulo, taken over by thousands of professional, amateur and para athletes, as well as ordinary citizens who are watching the traditional marathon held in the streets of some follow every January 1st, as part of the New Year's celebrations.

Nilson Pimenta da Costa, another naïve artist, from Caravelas, in the interior of Bahia state, presented at the 2010 of the Biennial of Brazilian Naïve Art the artwork *Moto Boy* [Motorcycle Courier Boy], whose theme was related to a series of murders committed by a young motorcycle courier – called a *motoboy* in Portuguese – who would meet young women, impress them by his charm, and then convince them to go with him to a large forested park in the city's South Zone where he would rape and kill them. The series of

crimes by the *motoboy* was sensationalized in the national media for a long time, converting this episode

Figure 15. Artist Nilson Pimenta da Costa, work *Moto Boy* [Motorcycle Courier Boy], 2010].

into an urban fabulation. The violence, terror and fear had an impact on the simple work of the popular artist, who depicts the countless victims, with details, including the roller skates the criminal used to charm his victims when he first met them at Ibirapuera

Park – another important icon of the city. The *motoboy's* crimes became part of the imaginaries of horror, fear, and urban ghosts of this artist who was living far from the great metropolis. The urban imaginaries thus stretch far and wide, even penetrating the minds of these popular artists at remote locations.

Another naïve artwork, presented at the 2008 edition of the Biennial of Brazilian Naïve Art, was by naïve artist Conceição Rodrigues Layon and entitled *O Caso Isabella* [The Case of Isabella]. This work

Figure 16. Artist artist Conceição Rodrigues Layon, work *O Caso Isabella* [The Case of Isabella], 2008.

describes the brutal murder of a five-year-old girl, committed by her father and stepmother, who threw Isabella out of the window of their six-story apartment. The girl's father tried to cover up the crime, forging evidence that made it look as though the child had fallen from the window. The story was all over the news for a long time, becoming one of the city's urban ghosts. Popular artist Conceição Rodrigues Layon resides in the interior of Minas Gerais state, and yet lent great meaning to the narrative of the crime, in consequence of the urban imaginaries.

These are just a few examples of many where the notion of the "citizen without the city" is demonstrated

by way of the artistic imaginations of these naïve artists who for the most part are very simple folk with little formal education, living in rural communities, completely removed from the large cities and yet are urban citizens.

In the same way that we identify a citizen who does not live in a city but is nevertheless an urban citizen since they recognize the ways of being urban, we find what Armando Silva calls urbanism without citizens – regions of the city that once had an urban signification, but which, for various reasons, are no longer recognized as urban spaces. These places are empty, abandoned, forgotten, and they lose their reference of urban marks. An example of this is the aforementioned case of SESC Belenzinho, which was built in a district that had once been a thriving community, but had then become an empty area of warehouses and cemeteries, with a lifeless urban imaginary. With the implantation of SESC Belenzinho, which entered the urban imaginary of the citizens as a sort of urban beach, the perception of the entire district was transformed into one of energy and life. Currently, the district is undergoing a process of revitalization. In this case, we see that the relationship of cause and effect between the imaginary city and the real city can work both ways: changes in the urban imaginaries can lead to transformations in the material city as well.

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